

Libyan Medical Journal: Re-Appearance and Challenges

Ahmed Atia^{1*}

Citation: Atia A, Glija A, Abusrewil S. Libyan Medical Journal: Re-Appearance and Challenges. 2022;14(1):1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5838175>

Copyright: © 2022 by the authors. Submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

¹ Department of Anesthesia and Intensive Care, Faculty of Medical Technology, University of Tripoli, Libya.

² Libyan Board of Medical Specialties, Tripoli, Libya

* **Correspondence:** ah.atia@uot.edu.ly

We are pleased to announce the reappearance of the Libyan Medical Journal (LMJ), formally known as *Jamahiriya Medical Journal (JMJ)* having been interrupted for the past 8 years. The current issue will be the first online issue under the updated name “Libyan Medical Journal” funded by the Libyan Board of Medical Specialties.

The editors are most grateful for all the founding editors, members of the editorial board who has served in any capacity since the beginning of the journal. At this time, we would like to extend our warmest greetings to the new members of the editorial board for the journal's upcoming re-release in 2022. The new board will be in charge of rebuilding the journal's webpage, which will be hosted by the Open Journal System (OJS) [1]. All editorial production processes, including copyediting, layout editing, and proofreading, are expected to be handled by the editorial board using the OJS system.

In this new stage, we would like to restate the standard terms and conditions for membership on the editorial board. Although the editorial board's leadership and membership are honorary positions with no financial compensation, it is mutually agreed that the members are committed to supporting the journal's welfare to the best of their abilities.

We are working to have this journal re-indexed in various online databases and search engines, which will improve its visibility and quality in order to meet global scholarly publishing standards.

Today, LMJ completes 20 years and steps into the fourth year of its stage, with the motivation to continual support of Libyan young scientist with their academic carrier particularly at different stages and landmarks to yield a productive work appear to the rest of the world despite the disappointing situation due to the COVID-19 outbreak. We should take the opportunity now to thank the authors for choosing LMJ as their means of sharing their outcomes and represent their insights. We also thank the reviewers and the editorial team for their unceasing support and perhaps most highly our readers who make it all valuable.

LMJ publishes reports in the medical, biomedical, life sciences, biotechnology, pharmacy, nursing, and other related fields. The journal makes its content available for free, which is likely to increase readership and citations [2]. Editorials, original articles, review articles, case reports, discussion papers, letters to the editor, and book reviews are all forms of reports that are published. LMJ also publishes abstracts from scientific meetings as conference proceedings. Commentaries or perspectives on current clinical or scientific issues within the scope of the journal may be considered. Furthermore, the article processing charge (APC) is presently waived.

Finally, we will continue to offer permissive copyediting and layout editing services, as many authors around the world may not be capable of producing a publishable document. We repeat our dedication to the journal's mission and invite all journal-related scholars to join us as authors, reviewers, and readers.

References

1. Open Journal Systems | Public Knowledge Project. Available from: <https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs/>
2. Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0). Available from: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>